

ISic1132

I.Sicily inscription 1132

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

altar

or base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 139

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 30.5 cm

Width 63.5 cm

Depth 48 cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Δωρόθεος Λυσ[---]
2. Ἄνταλλος Νύμφ[ωνος]
3. ἀγορανομήσαν[τες]
4. Ἀφροδίται
5. ἐκ τοῦ δήμου
6. γραμματεὺς
7. Ἀπολλόδωρος Φαλάκρου

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation (en)

Dorotheos Lys [— — —] Antallos son of Nymphon who were agoranomoi to Aphrodite.

[[by the people]] secretary (was) Apollodoros, son of Phalakros.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285044

EDCS 64900561

PHI 140617

Bibliography

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